

SPECIFIC FEATURES OF THE OCCURRENCE OF SITUATIONAL SEMANTICS IN THE UZBEK SPEECH

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ABSTRACT

This article deals with conveying specific features of the occurrence of situational semantics in the Uzbek speech. On the top of that there will be presented basic data and notions concerning about semantics in Uzbek language.

The philosophical units of form and meaning, their proportion, and their relationship to the event, in particular, are unique to the sentence. Two aspects characterize the synthetic structure, particularly the opposites of form and meaning: 1) disproportionate paradigm; 2) disproportionate synegmatic.

The appearance of the synthetic - semantic disproportion is based on the absence of two features or the excess of them, and it consists of the form and event as a result of their absence. The opposing sides of plenty's language are the language's spare principles, and the synthetic-semantic disproportion of simple sentences vanished on the basis of these principles. Sparing the meaning of compound forms represents sparing the methods of the language.

There are further compound sentences that lack the balance of form and meaning. It is well known that there are expressive meanings, and contrary terms such as "deictic sign" are utilized in compound phrases. The semantic properties of these words are indicated by the supplementary phrases. In conditional statements, these deictic markers reflect the disparity. The extra conditional sentences are the completeness, which is made up of the form and meaning, and is produced by the use of the opposing word in compound words. This term has no semantic value, yet it is communicated using conditional phrases.

The abundance principle only exists in form and is employed in phrases. «Two predicates that represent the event are employed in conditional phrases; it does not convey the major events, but it provides evidence to compound sentences» [3, p. 32]. There are two definitions of abundance in linguistics: 1) the unit that does not perform a function in sentences; 2) it is repeated in multiple semantics and has numerous meanings. The abundance reflects not just the thoughtologic or facultative meanings, but also the connotative and affective connotations. The abundance is regarded in two ways: first, as the particular abundance, and second, as the stylistic abundance.

There are two kinds of abundance principles: a) lexical abundance and b) grammatical abundance.

In creative and official style, lexical abundance is commonly employed. Grammar is commonly utilized in both spoken and written material.

Grammar is abundant in both simple and complicated phrases. Simple and complex phrases are comparable in their number of characteristics, yet they are not the same. In the synthetic structure of the sentences, the abundance characteristic to simple sentences is largely represented by asemantic vocabulary units. The vocabulary units detected by pronominalisation perform the role of asemantic form units. A man who reads a lot, for example, knows a lot. The dude is plenty in this statement. That is why we may adapt statements like: Who reads a lot, knows a lot.

The sentence structure is altered, while the meaning and synthetic structures remain unchanged. In the conditional clauses, the abundance principle is activated. Everyone respects the nice man, this synthetic creation must be shown by this, and everyone respects the men who are kind. The distinction between simple and complex sentences lies in the analysis and separation of meaning. In general, the plentiful creation of the synthetic system is one of the most important and attention-grabbing occurrences of these.

Polypredicative structures are supplied in compound sentences comprising abject, subject, complex object, predicate, and position, as well as simple phrases. For example, it is well recognized that honest individuals have honest souls. Denotative events are expressed by the general component of the compound sentences, the modus (It is known), and the extra sentences (the honest individuals have the honest spirit). The dictum of this statement is as follows: The labor of individuals with honest souls must be honest. It is the logic of the meaning that continues and does not differ from each other.

The sole difference between this denotative statement and others is the expression. This was the explanation for the imbalance of meaning and form - asymmetry.

There are some ways of disproportion are given: The disproportion represented by the proposition. The proposition of the disproportion is appeared by the adding two simple sentences. In this position, the main part and additional sentences are not the proposition, they represent the modus. The abundance principal works, only with the relation of the word in the modus which is expressed the event in the main sentences. Many times, when it is funny (qizig'i), it is good (yaxshisi), it is bad (yomoni) as the subject of the main part come like a quality, the denotative event changes into modus one, and it calls as the donative event of the additional conditional sentences. For example: It is funny, my aunt knows everything. – In this sentences, "it is funny" with modal meaning displays as the subject, in the result, the main part becomes modus event. The main information is informed by the additional sentences (she knows everything). We can observe such work when in order of object we use these verbs: bilmoq (to know), ko'rmoq (to see), aytmoq (to say), ta'kidlamoq (to consider), esda tutmoq (to remember), sedan chiqarmoq (to forget), payqamoq (to notice), ishonmoq (to believe), fahmlamoq (to conform), tushunmoq (to understand), ogoh bo'lmoq (be attentives), o'ylamoq (to think), qaror qilmoq (to make a decision), aniqlamoq (to find), tan bermoq (to subjugate), his etmoq (to feel), mo'ljalldamoq (to plan), shubhalanmoq (to doubt). These meaning is suit to the modus events. For example: The mother felt it, his son thought only about his stomach In

this sentence the object is “felt”, it comes as modus, and can be used as the introductory: The mother felt that, - By the feeling of mother we can see that in order to make a strong consider, we used it in the introductory place. Such position can be shown in many artistic works.

The disproportion caused by the synthesis of proportional terms. This disparity may be seen in both the primary and supplemental sentences, such as the response and inquiry. The direction section of the conditional phrases performs one synthetic function, while the others do the opposing synthetic function, resulting in the disproportion. For example, if one wishes to be great, one must set limitations for herself. The topic in this sentence is the direction component of two sentences. As a result, the direction elements are employed correctly in this statement. However, we have seen different ways: someone is nice, has many friends.

They are disproportional in this sentence because the direct element of the added sentence is the subject, whereas the predicate in the main phrase is the subject. In this statement, propositions such as: The courteous man has a lot of friends. As a result, we can see the disparity of form and meaning in the phrases below. If the conditional phrase has two predicative relations, one denotative event is expressed, and the abundance principle is used to emphasize the expressiveness. It is vital to remember that lingual disproportion plays a significant part in language appraisal, and it is not the sufficient wage for the sentences. This approach provides a clear understanding of the phrase by expressing the information smoothly.

This is seen in the following sentence: Who serves his people, everyone is proud of him. Who has the profession, one has the treasure (who - predicate, one - subject).

As a result, when sentences with plentiful principles make the proportion of form and meaning, the synthetic - semantic imbalance occurs. As a result, the disparity plays an important role in evaluating the language. It makes no difference; the disproportion is the property that is used to generate identical occurrences.

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